

ONTOHUMAN : ONTOLOGY-BASED INFORMATION EXTRACTION TOOLS WITH HUMAN-IN-THE-LOOP

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Motivation

Concurrent Engineering Facility

OVERVIEW

Developed, tested, and validated...
 Operational flexibility...
 Heritage...
 System components...

SPECIFICATIONS

- 1. Mass efficiency...
- 2. Power...
- 3. Long Duration...
- 4. Low Heat...
- 5. High Accuracy...
- 6. Low Error...
- 7. Low Error...
- 8. Low Error...
- 9. Low Error...
- 10. Low Error...

HERITAGE

Over 10 years...
 The PROTON...
 The PROTON...

SYSTEM COMPONENTS

μSTAR Tracker

Specifications table:

Parameter	Unit	Value	Value	Value	Value
Mass	kg	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Power	W	10	10	10	10
Longevity	yr	5	5	5	5
Accuracy	arcsec	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Heat	W	1	1	1	1
Error	arcsec	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Error	arcsec	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Error	arcsec	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Error	arcsec	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Error	arcsec	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1

Space Micro logo

jenaoptronik

Specifications table:

Parameter	Value
Mass	1.5 kg
Power	10 W
Longevity	5 yr
Accuracy	0.1 arcsec
Heat	1 W
Error	0.1 arcsec

Model-Based System Engineering Tool

- Goal: Automate the process of reading data sheets

Solution: Information Extraction x Ontology

Ontologies do not only introduce a sharable and reusable knowledge representation, but can also add new knowledge about the domain.

- Natural Language Processing
- Semantic Knowledge
- Ontology

Information Extraction + Ontology + Human = OntoHuman

System Overview

DSAT

- Intuitive way for annotating data
- **Auto-Detect** feature
- Annotations revision & **feedback** collecting

Information Extraction (PLIX)

- Ontology-based **key-value** pairs extraction

ConTrOn

- **Enrich ontologies** based on
 - extracted information from data sheets
 - external semantic knowledge base

DSAT Screenshot

The screenshot displays the DSAT interface for a document titled "Eagle Picher: Battery-15 EP-SAR-10197-DATA-SHEET". The interface is divided into several sections:

- Document Header:** Shows the document title and a search bar.
- Image Section (II):** Features an image of a battery pack with a callout box stating: "Lithium-ion provides higher energy levels and longer cycle life, at a lower weight and smaller volume, with less maintenance than lead acid, Ni-Cd, or Ni-MH batteries." Below the image is a "Features & Benefits" list and a "Specifications" table.
- Specifications Table:**

Specifications	
Part Number	SAB-10197
Weight Not to Exceed	140 lb/63.5 kg
Nominal Voltage	33.3V
Operating Voltage	27.0V to 35.8V
Beginning of Life Capacity/Energy	200Ah/6660WH @ 20°C
Maximum Dimensions	10.6"W x 29.5"L x 10.4"H
Specific Energy	104.9 Wh/kg
Operating Temperature	-5°C to 35°C
Survival Temperature (non-op)	-15°C to 40°C
Charge Current (Max)	100A
Maximum Continuous Discharge	154A
Maximum Discharge Pulse	400A for 1 sec
Random Vibe Levels	14 G RMS
Sine Vibe Levels	15G
Shock Level	1135G
- Applications:**
 - Military communications and surveillance
 - Commercial communication and broadcasting
 - NASA research
 - Environmental monitoring
 - Global navigation and tracking
- Annotation List (III):** A table listing key-value pairs with associated actions (edit, copy, delete, feedback).

Key	Value
Weight	63.5 kg
Dimensions	10.6"W x 29.5"L x 10.4"H
Weight	Not to Exceed 140 lb/63.5 kg
Shock	Level 1135G
Operating Temperature	-5°C to 35°C
reliability	> 0.99
Nominal Voltage	33.3V
Operating Voltage	27.0V to 35.8V
Survival Temperature	(non-op) -15°C to 40°C
Capacity	/Energy 200Ah/6660WH @ 20°C
Charge Current	(Max) 100A

- I. Select document
 - update metadata
 - update ontology
- II. PDF view
- III. Annotation list
 - edit item
 - copy
 - delete
 - feedback

DSAT : Ontology preview & update

The screenshot displays the DSAT ontology viewer interface. At the top, a title bar reads "Eagle Picher: Battery-15 EP-SAR-10197-DATA-SHEET". Below this, the main area is titled "View Ontology" and contains a network graph. The graph features a central node labeled "Class" with numerous other nodes connected to it, including "DischargeRate", "EnergyDensity", "DischargeRate", "EndOfDischarge", "DischargeCurrent", "EndOfChargeVoltage", "ContinuousDischargeCurrent", "DischargePuls", "ChargeRate", "SubClassOf", "DischargeRate", "EndOfDischarge", "DischargeCurrent", "EndOfChargeVoltage", "ContinuousDischargeCurrent", "DischargePuls", "ChargeRate", "SubClassOf", "DischargeRate", "EndOfDischarge", "DischargeCurrent", "EndOfChargeVoltage", "ContinuousDischargeCurrent", "DischargePuls", "ChargeRate", "SubClassOf". A popup window is overlaid on the left side of the graph, displaying metadata for a selected resource:

creator
license <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>
subject E-Commerce, E-Business, GoodRelations, ...
title ACCOM: The Accommodation Ontology for ...
versionInfo V 1.0, Release 2020-05-05

Select predicates for graph:

- owl#imports
- rdf-schema#isDefinedBy
- rdf-schema#subClassOf
- rdf-schema#subPropertyOf

Apply

Below the graph, there is a "Browse" button and a text input field containing "Or IRI, <http://purl.example.org/ex.owl> (no preview)". At the bottom right, there are "Reset", "Save", and "Cancel" buttons.

Auto-detect feedback

Eagle Picher: Battery-15 EP-SAR-10197-DATA-SHEET

Lithium-Ion provides higher energy levels and longer cycle life, at a lower weight and smaller volume, with less maintenance

Features & Benefits

- + Autonomous cell bypass capability
- + Primary and redundant heaters
- + Back-up temperature and voltage telemetry
- + Built-in cell safety protection
- + Current sense capability
- + Operational for 15-year mission life (GEO)
- + Space flight heritage
- + High reliability > 0.99
- + Built-in lifting points with detachable lifting fixture
- + Designed for radiation total-dose exposure of 3.11E6 rads
- + Connector savers for spacecraft integration and test bracket
- + Custom connectors are keyed and clocked per customer specification; MIL-DTL-38999 and/or NASA-5-311-P-768 connectors available upon request
- + Subjected to vibratory and thermal-vacuum testing

Auto-detected Annotation

nominal voltage 33.3V

Key Value Remark

was detected because
nominal voltage is a label of **supply voltage**

Correct

Incorrect, because ...

- the label should belong to
non operating shock
- something else:
different reason

Related terms: nominal voltage, voltage, DC Supply Voltage, DC Voltage, Supply Voltage,

Auto-Detect 1-2

Key	Value
Weight	63.5 kg
Dimensions	10.6"W x 29.5"L x 10.4"H
Weight	Not to Exceed 140 lb/63.5 kg
Shock	Level 1135G
Operating Temperature	-5°C to 35°C
reliability	> 0.99
Nominal Voltage	33.3V
Operating Voltage	27.0V to 35.8V
Survival Temperature	(non-op) -15°C to 40°C
Capacity	/Energy 200Ah/6660WH @ 20°C
Charge Current	(Max) 100A

New functions implemented in OntoHuman

- Correction of results from automatic information extraction (via feedback UI).
- Export of annotated information.
- Upload other ontologies for annotating documents.
- Support spreadsheets
- Option for processing specific pages instead of the whole document.
- Preview and display metadata of ontologies.
- Using multiple ontologies.

Live-Demo

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Eagle Picher: Battery-15 EP-SAR-10197-DATA-SHEET

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Specifications

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Sine Vibe Levels	15G
Shock Level	1135G

Applications

- + Military communications and surveillance
- + Commercial communication and broadcasting
- + NASA research
- + Environmental monitoring
- + Global navigation and tracking

⌵ ⌵
Auto-Detect 1-2
Search:

	Key	Value
✎ 🗑 🗑 🗑	Weight	63.5 kg
✎ 🗑 🗑 🗑	Dimensions	10.6"W x 29.5"L x 10.4"H
✎ 🗑 🗑 🗑	Weight	Not to Exceed 140 lb/63.5 kg
✎ 🗑 🗑 🗑	Shock	Level 1135G
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✎ 🗑 🗑 🗑	Charge Current	(Max) 100A

DSAT : Users Survey

Tool rating

Domain of Usage

Publications & Deliverables

- 2 workshops (July 2021, February 2022) with participants from NFDI4Ing community
- 1 NFDI Tool talk
 - <https://nfdi4ing.de/tooltalk-dsat>
- CDVE (Cooperative Design, Visualization and Engineering) paper (published in process)
 - September 2022
- Sourcecode & installation packages
 - <https://zenodo.org/record/6783007>

Outlook

- Published tutorials & source code
 - <https://nfdi4ing.de/tooltalk-dsat>
 - <https://zenodo.org/record/6783007>
- Extend the ontology preview with editing mode
- Currently detecting numerical values, but will include text value later
- Extend the auto-detect results with graph digitizer
- Ontology supporting multiple-languages keys

Frequency band	400.15 - 406 MHz
Plage de fréquences	400,15 - 406 MHz
Frequenzband	400.15 - 406 MHz